

Implementation of the Use of Digital Marketing as a Strategy to Strengthen Technopreneurship Resources

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ABSTRACT

Micro enterprises have a real contribution in economic growth in every region. It is necessary to strengthen the competence of business resources in the use of digital technology as an effort to grow technopreneurship, in the face of global competitiveness demands. To develop these competencies, skills, expertise, innovation and creativity are needed in the use of digital marketing platforms. However, there are still business actors who are not adaptive to these competencies. Community Service activities are expected to provide solutions to these problems in the form of skills counseling activities for the use of various digital marketing platforms with offline exposure, discussion and question and answer methods as well as simulations. Based on the results of the evaluation, the activity went well and the training material was in accordance with work needs. The follow-up needs a sustainability program with assistance to build technopreneurship and togetherness between business communities through the media of the Information/Communication Forum.

Keywords: Digital Marketing; Business Competence; Technopreneurship.

INTRODUCTION

A total of 42 partners have businesses in the fields of culinary, fashion, handicrafts, handycraft, Event Organizer and trade. From the results of profiling, dominated by female gender (83%), the age of participants is mostly between 41 – 50 years old with the type of business namely Culinary (64%), Fashion (21%), Services (7%) and Trade (7%). The position of Business Actors is generally Owner (98%). Regarding the business aspect, from the results of profiling, it can be seen that participants who have knowledge and marketing skills using digital platforms with a good category are only 7%, then Business Actors who are able to use digital marketing in their business are only 19%, Business Actors who are able to use Social

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Media in their business are only 21%. All business participants according to their needs expect to receive training in the form of digital marketing skills as a strategy to increase digital marketing sales and increase their network and business volume well.

Crucial problems that need to be overcome immediately include related to increasing the hard competency of Human Resources. Skills in the use of digital marketing technology that need to be utilized include social media with relevant soft competency support in the form of work ethic, mentality and high enthusiasm as a foundation for optimizing marketing in using digital marketing technology. The lack of hard competency requires the need for a strengthening strategy through the technical implementation of the use of digital marketing technology, so that every business actor grows into a reliable technopreneurship.

The basic ability to be able to use information technology in digital marketing business is a business demand as an effort to promote products and gain a competitive advantage in the global market. Based on this, the implementation team proposed the idea to hold Community Service activities with a method of counseling skills in the use of various digital marketing platforms with presentations, discussions and questions and answers as well as simulations using offline methods with the aim of increasing the hard competency as an effort to optimize the marketing of the resulting products. Through this activity, it is hoped that there will be continuity of coaching in terms of strengthening the skills of business actors' resources, considering that business actors need to utilize social media in marketing strategies and marketing mixes in their businesses (Utama, 2019).

RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

Competent human resources and supported by a resilient, strong and consistent mentality, spirit to optimize innovation and creativity of the products they produce so that they are competitive. Hadiyati (2011), Larsen & Lewis (2007), and Keeh, Nguyen, & Ping (2007) argue that small industry activities (MSMEs) can develop and achieve their goals if they have innovation and creativity in their production. According to Satria (2011), Darwanto (2013), and Yunal (2013), it is known that innovation and creativity are very helpful and have a significant influence on the development of business actors. Micro businesses and digital sales are increasing rapidly at this time. This increase also has a positive impact on the rate of economic growth in an area (Elly Wasliah, Head of Disdagin, February 25, 2022). This is due to an increase in online product purchases. The increase in business actors and online trade transactions has increased rapidly. As of 2022, business growth has increased to 180,000 new

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businesses. Meanwhile, online trade transaction activity increased by 150 percent.). This factor is driven by high purchasing power and people's shift to buy without face-to-face.

There are several problems faced by business actors, related to the attitude and behavior of technopreneurship businesses, namely: There is still a lack of ability to carry out online marketing, because the competence in using digital marketing facilities is not optimal due to helping to market the products produced. Business competition is getting tighter and requires adaptation to information technology, but MSME actors are not yet skilled in using digital marketing technical facilities.

In optimizing digital technology, innovation, creativity, as a marketing strategy, must always be adaptive to the dynamics of digital technology development as an effort to develop sustainable businesses in facing the global market. Based on the description above, the implementation of this community service activity is in the form of debriefing on the implementation skills of using digital marketing platform applications for business actors as a solution to several crucial problems faced by business actors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The method of implementing the activities used in this Community Service activity is explanation (presentation), discussion and question and answer as well as simulation using offline methods. This activity targets business actors who have gained understanding and knowledge of the use of digital technology based on the characteristics of technopreneurship, namely having a reliable mentality and spirit that has been conveyed in previous Community Service activities. The sustainability of coaching and mentoring business actors is a manifestation of the integration of human resource competencies, both hard and soft skills, so that business actors are able to make adjustments to the dynamics of global market competitiveness, in the form of creativity and innovation to optimize the use of digital platform facilities as strategic marketing techniques.

In the explanation of the material, the speakers conveyed the importance of the benefits and technicalities of using and preparing digital business facilities or facilities as a marketing strategy through various social media platforms. The delivery of the material will be supported by a visual display in the form of power point slides. In addition to paying attention to the speaker's description, the participants played an active role in discussions and questions and answers as well as technical simulations of the arrangement of facilities for various digital business platforms. Furthermore, the speakers also provided an opportunity for the participants' representatives to share their experiences regarding the technical use and preparation of social

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media facilities/facilities in marketing their products. The participants are expected to be enthusiastic about paying attention to the speaker's description and also active in questions and answers, discussions and simulations. Next, the speaker will explore information related to the obstacles faced by business actors in optimizing the technical use and arrangement of social media facilities/facilities in marketing business products.

Systematically the problem-solving framework that will be carried out in this activity is as follows: Determination of problems in business actors, namely related to the importance of technical skills in optimizing hard skills competencies related to the use and ownership of business digital facilities as a marketing strategy through various social media in the global market based on the creative and innovative spirit and mentality of business actors as the basis of competence. Some of the problems faced are the suboptimal use of social media by business actors and the limited understanding of business actors related to the use of digital business facilities as an effort to survive and have the opportunity to overcome competitiveness. The actors experienced several problems, namely a decrease in sales, difficulty in obtaining raw materials, inhibition of distribution, difficulties in capital, and inhibition of production.

The stages of implementing the activity as a solution offered to answer some of the problems faced are as follows: Meeting with representatives of the Bandung City Chamber of Commerce and confirmation related to the collection of data on prospective participants, especially participants who have received training in the activity. Socialization of activities to business actors. The implementation team worked together to prepare an activity plan. The implementation team prepared counseling materials. The implementation team prepares the activity schedule and prepares the needs of the activity. The implementation team carried out the activity in accordance with the plan that had been prepared. After the implementation of the activity, the Implementation Team conducts media publications and evaluates activities and prepares reports on these activities.

Community Service activities in the form of technical counseling on the use and preparation of digital business facilities and digital marketing are carried out offline. After the activity was carried out, evaluation and analysis were carried out through a qualitative approach by analyzing the data of the results of the questionnaire and the observation of participants in participating in the activity. The evaluation was carried out through a questionnaire submitted and filled out by the participants, both before and after the program was implemented with the aim of finding out to what extent the success of the program was achieved. In addition to filling out the questionnaire, recording and evaluating the obstacles faced by the participants related to the application of the counseling materials provided to the participants was also carried out. This is done to identify and find out the obstacles and solutions that are carried out to solve them and the sustainability of this activity by providing assistance to see the level of

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improvement in the implementation of the preparation and use of digital business facilities platforms as a marketing strategy.

The implementation of Community Service activities is carried out offline by providing education, socialization and simulations in the form of debriefing on the importance of strengthening Human Resources for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, with the character of technopreneurship that is globally competitive through skills in using social media platforms as a means of digital marketing. This activity began with a report by the Committee with a total of 42 participants, consisting of Culinary, Fashion, Event Organizer and Trade Business Actors. According to the observations of the Community Service Implementation Team, the participants were very enthusiastic and serious about participating in this activity. Participants were dominated by female gender (83%), the age of participants was mostly between 41 – 50 years old (38%), the type of business was Culinary (64%), Fashion (21%), Services (7%) and Trade (7%) with educational backgrounds as many as 15 people (36%) with high school education, 7 people (17%) with D3 education, 17 people (40%) with S1 education and as many as 3 people (7%) with S2 education. The age range is 7 people (17%) aged 20-30 years, 10 people (24%) aged 31-40 years, 16 people (38%) aged 41-50 years and as many as 9 people (21%) aged over 50 years, The application most used by participants is Instagram (41%). then Facebook (24%), Tiktok (18%), Youtube (11%) and the least used are Twitter (3%) and other applications (3%).

The position of Business Actors is generally Owner (98%). In the business aspect, especially the knowledge of digital marketing the participants are quite good (50%), then business actors who are able to use digital marketing in business as much as 45%, business actors who are able to use Social Media in their business by 50%. All business participants (100%) expect this training to increase their knowledge and skills in digital marketing and increase their network, so that their business grows. By participating in these trainings, the participants hope to improve their knowledge and skills. 98% of participants have a strong motivation to take part in the training until completion.

Participant Evaluation of the instructor according to pooling, it turned out that 95% stated that the instructor had good knowledge and broad insight with the material presented and motivated participants to actively participate in participating in the training. Instructors have the ability to self-adjust with the Trainees (97%), use delivery methods that are suitable for the participants (93%), and help the participants master the competencies they are trained (95%). The material followed was according to the needs of the participants (95%) and in accordance with the training theme (95%). The training material was delivered clearly and easily understood, so it was beneficial for the participants' businesses (95%). As for training facilities and infrastructure, the training space is clean and well organized (93%), all equipment and

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equipment during the implementation of the training are quite adequate (90%). The training location was clean and comfortable (97%) and consumption at lunch break was well served (97%). Meanwhile, for the satisfaction of the trainees, 100% of the participants stated that the training held was in accordance with expectations, and felt happy to participate in this training.

CONCLUSIONS

From the Community Service activities that have been carried out, it can be concluded as follows: The implementation of Community Service activities has run smoothly and in accordance with the planned schedule, starting from preparation, meetings with partners, implementation and evaluation. According to the preliminary study, the problems faced by business actors are; weak resources. Humans are both soft and hard skills, especially in the use of technology in facing the global market. From the results of the evaluation, most of the participants assessed that the implementation of activities and the readiness of the Committee were declared good (95%), the training materials were followed in accordance with work needs (95%), the training materials were delivered clearly and easily understood (95%), and the training materials were useful for business (98%). All equipment and equipment needed during the implementation of the training have been adequately available (96%) In terms of Trainers, the results of the evaluation of the Instructor have good knowledge and broad insight (98%), the Instructor has the ability to adjust himself with the trainees (99%), the Instructor motivates the participants to actively participate in the training provided (99%). In terms of training facilities and infrastructure are well available (96%) for upcoming activities, Participants conveyed several inputs, including; Activities like this should be carried out regularly, then expect further training. Based on these conclusions, it can be recommended as follows: For the Bandung City Chamber of Commerce, it is necessary to build sustainable programs for business actors, especially those related to strengthening Human Resources to be able to keep up with the times and be able to be globally competitive For business actors, it is necessary to build a spirit of togetherness between members of the business actor community through a media or Information/Communication Forum. For community service teams, it is necessary to follow up with follow-up programs to help with mentoring.

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